

EVOLUTION OF CRYSTALLINE PARAMETERS DURING STABILIZATION OF POLYACRYLONITRILE FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Textile polyacrylonitrile fibers showing different effective diameters were stabilized under air. The evolution of crystalline parameters of these fibers during stabilization was investigated. For this purpose samples at different levels of stabilization as determined by differential scanning calorimetry were analysed by x-ray diffraction. Crystalline parameters, such as crystallite size and inter-planar spacing, were examined. At the initial stages of stabilization, the size and the orientation of the crystallites increase significantly as function of temperature or exothermic energy release. After further progression of the exothermic stabilization reaction, crystallite size and crystallite orientation decrease drastically. A direct correlation of these crystalline parameters appears to exist. The inter-planar spacing changes at clearly higher temperatures or exothermic energy release. All crystalline parameters and their evolution as function of stabilization are similar for fibers with different effective diameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibers are widely used as precursor material for carbon fiber production. Before carbonization, the thermoplastic, semi-crystalline PAN fibers are stabilized in a thermal treatment under air. This stabilization process, which is the time limiting step of carbon fiber production, influences the mechanical properties of the resulting carbon fibers. However, the chemical reactions and the structural and chemical evolution of PAN fibers during stabilization are still subject of research. Many investigations addressing this topic have been performed using infrared spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance, differential scanning calorimetry, densitometry, thermogravimetry, small-angle x-ray diffraction or wide-angle x-ray diffraction (WAXS) [1]. In the actual work we focus on the evolution of crystalline parameters during the stabilization process as measured by WAXS starting with textile PAN fibers as obtained from a wet spinning process.

Based on WAXS results on PAN fibers, two crystal structures are discussed in literature, i.e. a hexagonal structure [2] and an orthorhombic structure. The occurrence of the orthorhombic structure is attributed to co-crystallized solvents [3] or water [4]. Ref. [5] calculated a diffraction pattern with the assumption of pseudo-hexagonal and atactic planar zigzag, which shows two reflections perpendicular to the fiber axis corresponding to 0.52 nm and 0.30 nm. The ratio of the two strong reflection spacings is $\sqrt{3}$ [6], in agreement with the work presented here.

Many authors analyzed the change of the crystalline parameters during preheating [7-9] and stabilization [10-24] with wide-angle x-ray diffraction. These results are discussed in detail in comparison to our work.

In the following, we present a WAXS study of textile PAN fibers after different heat treatment steps. Three different types of fibers are used, differing in their effective diameter. The fibers are stabilized to different degrees, to investigate the changes of crystalline parameters as function of stabilization. Additionally, the influence of the fiber diameter on the crystalline order is addressed. The investigation of textile PAN fibers allows general conclusions about the PAN stabilization process and gives valuable information also for technical PAN fiber processing.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Sample preparation

Three types of textile polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibers L900 from Dralon were investigated. The fibers are produced by wet spinning and consist of 93 % acrylonitrile and 7 % vinyl acetate [25]. The fibers have titers of 1.3 dtex, 3.3 dtex and 5.6 dtex, which correspond to effective diameters of 11.8 μm , 18.9 μm and 24.6 μm . The effective diameter is calculated assuming a perfect cylindrically formed fiber. A furnace with air flow is used to stabilize bundles of fibers. A constant heating rate of 5 K/min up to 180 °C and then of 1.25 K/min up to a specific target temperature is chosen. The different target temperatures represent different degrees of stabilization, which are calculated from differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), as described below. After reaching the target temperature, the bundle of fibers is removed from the furnace to stop the stabilization progress. During the stabilization a Zwick/Roell universal testing machine with a 5 N load cell keeps the fibers under a tension of 0.58 MPa.

2.2 Differential scanning calorimetry

The DSC-measurements were carried out using a DSC 204 F1 Phoenix ASC from Netzsch in synthetic air. The gas flow rate was 50 ml/min. The heating rate was 1.25 K/min. We cut the fibers into short pieces with a length of a few millimeters. Fibers with an initial weight of about 3 mg are placed in an aluminum pan with 5 holes in the cap. The degree of stabilization was determined using the exothermic energy release of the reaction as measured by DSC. To this end, we subtract a baseline from the DSC-curves, as shown in Figure 1. Integration of the resulting heat flow over temperature up to the respective target temperature yields the exothermic energy release generated during the various stabilization processes. The different target temperatures are given in Figure 4.

Figure 1: DSC-curve of PAN fiber including baseline.

2.3 X-ray Diffraction

We use a Seifert PTS x-ray diffractometer with a copper anode to measure the crystal structure of PAN and stabilized PAN fibers. Fibers were measured as function of the angles 2θ and χ , as shown in Figure 2. The fiber bundles are oriented perpendicular to the diffraction plane during the 2θ -measurement. During the χ -measurement the 2θ -angle is kept at the position of the (100) reflection, while the angle χ is varied.

Figure 2: WAXS geometry. Red: fiber bundle, blue: detector, yellow: x-ray source. (a) 2θ -geometry and (b) χ -geometry.

Analysis of the WAXS 2θ -measurement (Figure 3a) proceeds in four steps: Firstly, we subtract an experimentally determined zero-background. Secondly, we subtract a spline-background to account for scattering from amorphous regions. Thirdly, we fit an asymmetric pseudo-Voigt curve to the two reflections. Finally, the inter-planar spacing and the crystallite size are determined applying the Bragg equation and the Scherrer formula ($k = 0.89$), respectively, to the parameters of the fit of the first reflection at $2\theta = 16.9^\circ$. Instrumental broadening is taken into account. In addition, the crystallinity is determined by the ratio of the integral intensity of the reflection and the integral intensity of the spline-background.

The χ -measurement (Figure 3b) is used to determine the orientation of the crystallites to the fiber axis. The experimental curve is fitted by an asymmetric pseudo-Voigt curve. The width at half maximum is used to determine the crystallite orientation f_c , following Refs. [26, 27]. It should be pointed out that the crystallite orientation, as determined from a single fiber by synchrotron WAXS, results in higher values than the bundle measurements [28]. This could be a result of the slight misalignment of the high number of fibers within a bundle relative to each other.

Figure 3: Exemplary x-ray diffraction patterns: (a) 2θ -measurement with two asymmetric pseudo-Voigt-fits. (b) χ -measurement with one asymmetric pseudo-Voigt-fit.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows the measured DSC curves of the three textile PAN fibers with different effective diameters. The maximum of exothermic heat flow is found at about 280°C for all three fiber types. However, the absolute value of heat release differs. The maximal heat flow is highest for the fiber with a diameter of $11.8\ \mu\text{m}$. It decreases with increasing fiber diameter and is minimal for the fiber with a diameter of $24.6\ \mu\text{m}$. This is probably an effect of the volume to surface ratio.

The target temperatures, representing different degrees of stabilization, are marked by coloured squares in Figure 4. The target temperatures cover the range from the onset to the maximum of the

exothermic DSC signal and thus allow an investigation of the effect of progressing stabilization by XRD analysis of the respective fibers.

Figure 4: DSC-measurement of the three types of PAN fibers. Squares mark the target temperatures.

In our x-ray diffraction 2θ -measurements only two reflections at 16.9° and 29.5° are observed (see Figure 3a). The ratio of the inter-planar spacing in (100) and (110) direction of the initial PAN fibers amounts to almost $\sqrt{3}$, in agreement with a pseudo hexagonal structure [6]. The inter-planar spacing calculated from the first reflection amount to about 0.525 nm for all three PAN fibers, in agreement with values observed for copolymerised PAN fibers in literature [9, 14, 21, 23, 29].

Initial heat treatment leaves the inter-planar spacing unchanged up to target temperatures of 270 °C, as shown in Figure 5a. This is in agreement with Refs. [9, 15, 17, 21, 23, 29], who observe a constant inter-planar spacing for heat treatments below 240 °C. Above 270 °C a significant increase of the inter-planar spacing is observed, until for temperatures of about 300 °C an inter-planar spacing of more than 0.545 nm is found. This is in agreement with Refs. [9, 15, 17, 21, 23, 29]. The trend of the inter-planar spacing as function of temperature is the same for the three types of fibers showing different effective diameters. The stabilization reaction, i.e. the oxidation of the PAN molecules, induces a drastic change of the molecular structure. Still under these conditions reflections of PAN crystallites are observed and initially remain unaffected.

To correlate the changes of inter-planar spacing to the progress of the stabilization reaction, in Figure 5b the inter-planar spacing is plotted as function of exothermic energy release during stabilization. For exothermic energies releases up to 1200 J/g the inter-planar spacing of the crystallites remains almost constant, even though a considerable heat flow is observed, indicating a substantial progress of stabilization. At energies above 1200 J/g the inter-planar spacing increases significantly. Only here, the structure of the crystallites appears affected by the progressing oxidation.

Figure 5: Inter-planar spacing of the stabilized fibers with diameters of 11.8 μm , 18.9 μm and 24.6 μm (a) in dependence of the target temperature and (b) in dependence of the exothermic energy release.

Focussing on the initial stage of the stabilization, i.e. at low exothermic energy release, a slight minimum of the inter-planar spacing is observed at 400 J/g (see Figure 6). Here, the inter-planar spacing varies between values of 0.524 nm and 0.526 nm. At low stabilization progress thus a slightly closer packing of the molecular chains is observed. With ongoing stabilization, this effect is reversed and the increase in inter-planar spacing as described above starts. Fibers with different effective diameters show the same dependence on exothermic energy release.

Figure 6: Inter-planar spacing of the stabilized fibers with diameters of 11.8 μm , 18.9 μm and 24.6 μm in dependence of the exothermic energy release.

The crystallite size of the three types of fibers as function of target temperature is plotted in Figure 7a. For the initial PAN fiber a crystallite size of about 8 nm is found. No difference exists in crystallite size between the fibers with different effective diameters. With increasing target temperature a significant increase of crystallite size is found. At a temperature of 250 °C all three fiber types reach their maximal crystallite size. For the fibers with diameter of 11.8 μm and 18.9 μm the maximal crystallite size is very similar, reaching values of 16.5 nm and 17.0 nm, respectively. This corresponds to an increase of about 110 % of the initial value. The fiber with a diameter of 24.6 μm shows an even higher crystallite size of 19 nm, corresponding to an increase of about 140 %. At temperatures above 250 °C a drastic decrease of crystallite size to a value of about 1 nm is observed. A similar behavior is found by Refs. [17, 21, 23, 30-35]. Crystallite size values from 3.8 nm [9] to 14.5 nm [23] for PAN and maximal values ranging from 5.7 nm [13] to 22.7 nm [23] for PAN during stabilization are presented in literature. The increased crystallite sizes achieved by low temperature thermal treatment of the textile PAN fibers are among the highest values described in literature. Thus a drastic change of the crystalline properties of the textile fibers occurs before and even during the stabilization reactions takes place.

In Figure 7b the crystallite size is plotted as function of the exothermic energy release. The increase of crystallite size occurs at the very beginning of the exothermal reaction. Maximal crystallite size is realised at an exothermic energy release of 180 J/g for all three types of fibers. The decrease of crystallite size starts above 180 J/g and the crystallite size attains values of about 1 nm at 1500 J/g.

While the crystallite size starts to decrease at an exothermic energy release of 180 J/g, the inter-planar spacing starts to increase at a clearly higher energy release of 1200 J/g. The fact that the crystallites maintain their order and initially even grow during the stabilization reaction indicates that they show a higher stability against the chemical reactions associated with the stabilization process compared the other PAN material. At an energy release of 1200 J/g, at which the inter-planar spacing starts to change, the crystallite size has already decreased by more than a factor of two to about 8 nm. This might indicate that there exists a critical crystallite size for this effect to occur.

Figure 7: Crystallite size of the stabilized fibers with diameters of 11.8 μm, 18.9 μm and 24.6 μm (a) as function of the target temperature and (b) as function of the exothermic energy release.

In Figure 8 the crystallite orientation, as defined by Ref. [26], is plotted as function of target temperature and exothermic energy release. The crystallite orientation of all three types of fiber shows a similar temperature dependence as the crystallite size. For temperatures up to 250 °C it increases from 0.6 to 0.87 with increasing temperature and then decreases drastically. As function of exothermic energy release the decrease starts at 180 J/g. Thus the crystalline parameters crystallite size and crystal orientation appear to be directly linked to each other. The absolute values for the orientation are in good agreement with that found in literature. Here values of 0.78-0.95 are given [36, 37].

Figure 8: Orientation f_c of the stabilized fibers with diameters of 11.8 μm, 18.9 μm and 24.6 μm (a) as function of the target temperature and (b) as function of the exothermic energy release. Error of measurement is indicated for the first point of each measured curve.

Figure 9 shows the crystallinity of the fibers as function of target temperature and exothermic energy release. The crystallinity of all three fiber types remains at a value of about 0.43 up to a target temperature of 250 °C. For higher temperatures it decreases to almost zero. In literature crystallinity values of 0.36-0.58 are common, which is in good agreement with our results [36, 37]. As function of exothermic energy release the decrease of crystallinity starts at about 180 J/g. Again, this is very similar to the behavior of the crystallite size, indicating a direct link of the two parameters.

Figure 9: Crystallinity of the stabilized fibers with diameters of 11.8 μm , 18.9 μm and 24.6 μm (a) as function of the target temperature. (b) as function of the exothermic energy release. Error of measurement is indicated for the first point of each measured curve.

Comparing the results, we notice that crystallite size, crystallite orientation and crystallinity behave similar as function of target temperature and of exothermic energy release for all three types of fibers. All these crystalline parameters show a maximum at a target temperature of 250 °C corresponding to an exothermic energy release of 180 J/g. A high crystallinity thus is correlated to both, a high crystallite size and a high crystallite orientation. Below 250 °C or 180 J/g a clear increase of crystallite size and crystallite orientation is found, while the crystallinity remains constant or increases only slightly. This indicates that larger crystallites grow at the expense of smaller crystallites resulting in an increase of crystallite size and orientation in the same time, while the crystallinity remains almost constant.

The maximal value of crystalline parameters at 180 J/g is followed by a drastic decay at higher energy releases. Here a significant oxidation of the PAN molecules and a drastic change of the microstructure takes place. The crystalline PAN regions are converted to an amorphous network structure. The observed decrease of crystallinity is linked to a decrease of both, crystallite size and orientation.

It should be noted that exothermic stabilization reaction has already proceeded to a certain extent before crystalline parameters start to fall off. This indicates, that stabilization reaction starts within the amorphous regions of the fiber [11, 13]. Only after further progression of the stabilization reaction also the crystalline regions are affected, in agreement with literature [38]. This indicates higher stability of the crystalline regions compared to the amorphous regions. The inter-planar spacing, however, is stable up to much higher exothermic energies of about 1200 J/g. The change of inter-planar spacing occurs at a crystallite size of 8 nm for all three types of fibers, suggesting a critical crystallite size for this effect to occur.

4 CONCLUSION

The evolution of crystalline parameters of textile PAN fibers during stabilization were investigated by WAXS measurements. Fibers were stabilized to different degrees, to investigate the changes of crystalline parameters during stabilization progress. To address the influence of the fiber diameter, three chemically identical textile fibers with different effective diameters are investigated.

At the initial stage of stabilization reaction, a significant increase of crystallite size and crystallite orientation is observed as function of temperature or exothermic energy release. A direct correlation of these crystalline parameters appears to exist. The increase of crystallite size and orientation follows the same temperature dependence, while crystallinity remains almost constant suggesting a growth of larger crystallites on the expense of smaller ones. Thus a significant change of the crystalline properties of the textile fibers occurs with a possible influence of the following stabilization reaction. The fact that in the initial stage of the stabilization reaction an increase of crystallite size and

orientation is observed suggests that the stabilization reaction starts within the amorphous regions of the fiber. After further progression of the stabilization reaction, a clear decay of crystalline parameters is found, resulting from changes in molecular structure. The interplanar spacing appears to change at a critical crystallite size at clearly higher temperatures and exothermic energy release.

All crystalline parameters and their evolution as function of stabilization progress are similar for the three types of fibers with different diameters investigated.

It is interesting to note that the size of crystallites as determined by WAXS is of the order of the diameter of nano-fibrils expected for these types of fibers [39, 40]. It can be speculated that these two parameters are correlated.

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